

THE MAIN PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL FORMATION OF STUDENTS

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Abstract

The article discusses the main pedagogical conditions that contribute to the professional and personal development of students. The main conditions discussed are the use of personality-oriented teaching technologies, the formation of professional values and ethical standards, the development of practical skills, the creation of a favorable professional environment and the development of mentoring and coaching methods. The systematic creation and implementation of pedagogical conditions for improving the personal qualities, values and abilities of students increases their responsible attitude to future professions. The emphasis is on the fact that the process of professional development is organized, managed and controlled. The pedagogical conditions that influence the professional development of students in the learning process are defined and described.

Keywords: professional personality, student, pedagogical conditions, professional formation, skills, higher education institution, professional values, professional environment, mentoring.

One of the main tasks facing the education system in the era of globalization is the formation of competitive, competent, professionally trained specialists. The formation of professional and personal qualities of students is one of the most important tasks not only of educational institutions, but also of society as a whole. The development of professional and personal qualities of students at the university ensures their success in the future labor market. In this direction, the importance of pedagogical conditions that contribute to the improvement of personal qualities, the development of values and abilities of students increases. To implement any pedagogical phenomenon in any educational process, it is necessary to create a certain set of conditions. Before defining the main pedagogical conditions for the professional and personal development of students, first of all, let us analyze the concept of "pedagogical conditions". In pedagogy, "conditions" are defined as factors on which the effectiveness of the functioning of the pedagogical system depends [1].

In pedagogical research, the concept of a contract is considered as factors, situations, and measures that determine the effective functioning and development of the pedagogical system. The methodological analysis of pedagogical conditions is reflected in the work of Y. K. Babansky, V. I. Andreev, N.Y. Postalyuk and others. Under the pedagogical condition, Y. K. Babansky understands a situation when the components of the educational process interact with each other and create an opportunity for teachers to work productively, manage the educational process, and for students to work successfully [2].

Domestic and foreign scientists have studied various aspects of this process and prepared a number of recommendations aimed at improving the professional and personal development of students. In this regard, it is possible to identify several pedagogical conditions

for the professional and personal development of students:

The use of technologies of personality-oriented learning. Personality-oriented learning is an effective method aimed at taking into account the individual abilities, interests and developmental characteristics of each student. For example, each student may have their own learning style: one understands visual material better, while others absorb information faster with the help of practical tasks. The use of such teaching methods helps to increase students' interest in classes and develop their creative potential. The works of the Russian scientist, Doctor of Psychology K. B. Zharylbaev widely examine the relationship in the field of personality development and education. He emphasized that the main goal of the education system is not only for students to gain knowledge, but also to improve their professional and personal qualities [3].

Foreign scientists are also studying the importance of personality-oriented learning. For example, the American researcher J. Dewey proved the need to create favorable conditions for the self-development of the individual, that his active participation in the educational process increases the effectiveness of the educational process. In his opinion, education should be aimed at developing the individual interests and creative potential of each student [4].

Formation of professional values and ethical standards. Professional values and ethical standards determine the responsibility, honesty and diligence of students as future specialists. Kazakh scientist Abdigapparova A. E. shows the importance of teaching ethical standards in the formation of professional and personal qualities of students. In his works, the main pedagogical task is considered to be the assimilation of professional moral values by students in the educational process [5]. E. Shane studied the influence of

professional ethics on personal values. In his opinion, ethical values and standards develop students' ability to make decisions based on moral responsibility and integrity in a professional environment [6].

To form professional values and ethical standards, special courses and trainings can be held in an educational institution. This teaches students to be prepared for various moral dilemmas. For example, future educational psychologists are taught such important values as maintaining confidentiality when working with a client.

Development of practical skills. An important place in the professional development of students at universities is occupied by the development of practical skills. In order to develop students' ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, special attention must be paid to professional practice in an educational institution. In her research, the teacher, specialist in the field of education and scientist Kudaibergenova M. Zh. emphasizes the importance of practical skills in preparing students for their future profession. She emphasizes the need to ensure consistency between theory and practice in the educational process. In addition, she puts forward the need to improve students' professional skills by applying their knowledge in practice [7].

Theory and practice are closely linked in the dual education system of Germany. In addition to studying within this system, students work at production sites every semester to gain professional experience. As a result, they, along with a diploma, gain the necessary experience, which gives a great advantage when finding a job.

American psychologist, scientist D. Kolb in his research examines the effectiveness of learning based on experience, and argues that students should not only theoretically apply knowledge, but also hone their experience, applying it in practice. According to D. Kolb, "learning is practice" and students' gaining professional experience at universities has a positive effect on their professional and personal development [8].

Creating a favorable and developing professional environment. Creating a favorable environment for the professional development of students contributes to their improvement as future specialists. In this environment, students have the opportunity to share their new ideas and conduct an open dialogue with colleagues and teachers. A supportive environment increases students' confidence and promotes the development of personal initiatives. In world psychology, in the theory of socio-cultural development of the Soviet psychologist L. S. Vygotsky, a supportive environment is considered the most important factor in the development of personal qualities of a person. In his opinion, human abilities develop due to the social environment, therefore the educational environment should support and allow students to develop [9]. The motivation theory of the representative of humanistic psychology A. Maslow reveals the importance of creating a supportive environment for students. Maslow notes that through a supportive environment, a person's desire for self-development increases, which, in turn, contributes to the professional and personal development of students [10].

Development of mentoring and coaching. Mentoring and coaching play a major role in improving students' professional competence. In mentoring programs, experienced professionals provide students with guidance, professional advice, and help them define their professional goals. For example, in many US higher education institutions, mentoring programs help students adapt and define professional goals.

One of the scientists who conducted research on mentoring in Kazakhstani pedagogy is Satpayeva R.K. She argues that mentoring is a necessary method in a higher education institution for teaching students to master professional skills and apply them in practical practice [11]. Among foreign scientists, T. Scatcher and B. Parsons studied whether the widespread use of mentoring and coaching in a professional environment allows students to fully realize their potential and develop professionally. In their research, mentoring is an effective pedagogical tool that helps students manage themselves and achieve their personal goals [12]. Thus, the professional and personal development of students at a university is a complex process that shapes their professional qualifications and personal qualities as future specialists. Research by domestic and foreign scientists shows the importance of pedagogical conditions in ensuring the professional and personal development of students. Through personally oriented training, the formation of professional values and ethical standards, the development of practical skills, the creation of a favorable environment and the development of mentoring, it is possible to create favorable conditions for the professional and personal development of students. By effectively using these pedagogical conditions, educational institutions can ensure that students become competitive and competent specialists in their field. Pedagogical conditions aimed at the professional and personal development of students allow them to play an important role in society in the future.

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